

BABOTS

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*BABOTS:
The design and control of small swarming
biological animal robots*

Ethics framework (Part I)

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*This is primarily an **ethics** framework and not a regulatory one. On the one hand, the framework goes deeper into the ethical matters than regulations would require but, on the other, it does not overtly concern itself with detailed technical matters that are already overseen by institutional ethics review boards and national and international rules and regulations.*

The framework is part of the WP4, Task 4.1. that runs through months 1-48. This first part (the basics) of the ethics framework is delivered on the 30th of September. The groundwork for the deliverable has been conducted by the Aalto team and based on their bioethical expertise, but the specifics pertaining to Babots have been identified and developed in interaction with WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP5 at project meetings and in one-to-one communications. All the expected work so far has been done and the work in WP4 is progressing as planned.

1. Balancing harms and benefits

At its core, research ethics is about balancing harms and benefits, widely construed.¹ In what follows the basic ethical issues pertinent to the “Babots: The design and control of small swarming biological robots” project are explicated.

2. Harms to *Caenorhabditis elegans* in research?

2.1 No harm?

*In general, *C. elegans* are considered compliant with the 3R rules of animal experimentation. As invertebrates they do not currently even fall under the animal welfare regulations in the EU. The traditional view is that there are “no ethical issues” when doing research on *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*).² Sometimes this has been seen as such a self-evident truth that no reasons or references are given.³ The idea behind the position is that as very simple form of life, *C. elegans* cannot be harmed in any meaningful sense.*

2.2 Sentience?

However, recent studies have slowly begun to question this basic assumption. In a 2022 article in the journal *Animal Sentience*, Crump et al. proposed 8 criteria for sentience: Nociception, Sensory integration, Integrated nociception, Analgesia (endogenous and exogenous), Motivational trade-offs, Flexible self-protection, Associative learning, and Analgesia preference (self-administer, location, and prioritized)⁴. While their study concentrated on decapod crustaceans – a considerably more complex life form than *C. elegans* – later commentary papers applied the criteria to *C. elegans*. In her article, Elizabeth Ervine showed that *C. elegans* satisfies 3 of Crump et al.’s criteria; Nociception, Analgesia, and Analgesia preference. She, however, went on to argue that since not all the criteria for sentience are equal and *C. elegans* fails to meet most of the other ones, including the crucial Sensory integration, *C. elegans* probably is not sentient after all.⁵ In another commentary, Kristin Andrews is less certain of the lack of sentience in *C. elegans*. She points to other

studies on, and other definitions of, animal sentience and concludes that there are reasons to assume that more animals than previously assumed are indeed sentient.⁶

The evidence regarding the sentience of *C. elegans* is not conclusive either way, but for now, the “not-sentient” side still seems better justified. It should be noted though that even if it later transpires that *C. elegans* has some minimal level of sentience, it would not automatically render Babots unethical. It would change the harms and benefits ratio but given the potential benefits of the research and the arguably very minor harms to *C. elegans*, the research would still most likely be deemed ethical.⁷ Also, if sentience would be present that might allow the researchers to use such positive enforcements as “pleasure”.

The question of possible sentience is very new in connection to *C. elegans* research. We will be closely monitoring the situation and adjust the harm-benefit assessments should that become necessary.

2.3 As living beings?

Even if *C. elegans* are not sentient, and do not fall under the EU regulation concerning animal welfare, they might still, as living beings, be worthy of being treated well. The Directive 2010/63/EU states that “[a]nimals have an intrinsic value which should be respected”.⁸ However, given that the directive as a whole does not apply to invertebrates, it is not sure whether *C. elegans* count as “animals” there. Be that as it may, there are various philosophical and ethical schools of thought that hold that as living beings *C. elegans* deserve some respect.

Religions are among the oldest ethical authorities and while much mistreatment of animals and nature more generally has been done in the name of religions, especially the monotheistic ones, most world religions also include an idea of stewardship, humans’ special responsibility towards other animals and the nature as a whole.⁹ According to the United Nation’s Environmental Programme “[a]ll religions agree that nature is an act of divinity and should be treated as such.”¹⁰

Thinkers of the Enlightenment seldom had much to say about the treatment of non-human animals. Immanuel Kant’s idea that we have an indirect duty not to treat animals with cruelty is an oft-cited exception. Kant did not value non-human animals as such but thought that we should avoid cruelty to animals because that would make us more prone to act with cruelty towards our fellow human beings.¹¹ Following this line of thinking it would be advisable to treat *C. elegans* with respect as that would show a good example to those doing research with more complex life forms.

The idea that animals have intrinsic value didn’t really start to gain ground in Western philosophy until the 20th century. One of the pioneers of this thinking was a German theologian and educator Fritz Jahr, who in the 1920s started to express strong views about the treatment of non-human life.^{12,13} Like Albert Schweitzer a little later,¹⁴ Jahr believed in reverence and awe towards all forms of life. As a physician, Schweitzer famously agonized about killing micro-organisms to cure his patients.¹⁵ Since the times of Jahr and Schweitzer, animal ethics and environmental ethics have increased in popularity and even developed into their own fields of study. Within both fields there is great variety in terms of the reasons for respecting non-human life and the degrees of respect warranted, but the shared view is the recognition of some value in non-human life.

As noted, the EU legislation doesn’t currently require animal welfare regulations to be applied when dealing with animals such as the *C. elegans* but given the expansion of the

kinds of living beings that we are seeing as worthy of moral concern in the past century, it is conceivable that sometime in the future, *C. elegans* too are seen as worthy of respect.

Those who upheld a strict reading of the so-called “precautionary principle” might see the current uncertainty as a strong enough a reason not to involve even the lower animals, such as *C. elegans* in research. The precautionary principle states, roughly, that when there is a possibility of harm, we should not proceed even if there is no actual evidence of the harm, and that the burden of proof lies with those who claim there is no harm.¹⁶ However, such an interpretation of the principle would render most our actions, and almost all research unethical, and would be, as such, impossible to uphold.

2.4 Using one species to benefit others?

In addition to welfare concerns, one of the reasons why the EU and other similar actors are striving to ultimately replace animal use in research and testing altogether,¹⁷ is that there seems to be something wrong about using one group of beings to benefit another. For instance, in human research ethics, when research is conducted on vulnerable groups, it is required that the research will benefit that group.¹⁸ Arguably all animals used in research are in a vulnerable position in relation to humans conducting the research, yet they very seldom benefit from the research conducted.¹⁹

3. Harm in genetic engineering

3.1 Harmed by being genetically altered?

If we believe that *C. elegans* cannot be harmed by research conducted on them, it would seem to follow that they would not be harmed by being genetically altered either. However, if we subscribe to any form of teleological thinking – the idea that all beings have a natural telos towards which they naturally move and should move – genetic engineering becomes more susceptible.

3.2 Genetic engineering is wrong because it is unnatural?

In ethics and philosophy, the roots of teleological thinking are in Aristotle.²⁰ His ideas were later developed into Natural Law theory by Thomas Aquinas and others.²¹ Suffice to state here that those subscribing to natural law theory would be averse to going against “the natural order of things”. Interfering with natural evolution is what makes genetic engineering in this framework wrong. While it is clear that *if* there is something wrong with going against the untampered order of things, genetic engineering would be a paragon example of the wrong, it is less clear, however, why the line should be drawn there. Most of, say, Western medicine is geared to fight the natural processes of aging, and cultivating land interferes with natural ecosystems, yet few are calling a complete stop to these practices.

Those subscribing to the natural law theory are, however, not the only ones who are concerned about the “unnaturalness” of genetic engineering. “Unnaturalness” is often evoked by ordinary people who have never even heard of natural law theory. In that context, the utterances of “unnaturalness” often convey feelings uncertainty, fear, and uneasiness caused by matters that are unfamiliar or unusual rather than any well justified moral stances.

Equating “natural” with moral and “unnatural” with immoral has the further problem that there are many natural phenomena, such as hurricanes and draughts, illnesses and injuries that we do not think as good or moral. And while “the survival of the fittest” might be the rule by which natural evolution operates, hardly anyone would wish that to become our guiding principle of morality.²²

3.3 Genetic engineering is wrong because it is Playing God?

For some people, the wrongness of genetic engineering is that it is seen as an act of “playing God”. The argument from Playing God can be given both a religious and a secular reading. In the former, someone is playing God when they are doing things that are only for God to do and in the latter, “God” is taken in a more metaphorical sense. There, “God” refers to an omnipotent and omniscient being, who knows all the consequences of its actions and the argument is most often evoked as a warning against hubris. Humans are not all-knowing and all-powerful and therefore, they should not engage in activities that could have disastrous and far-reaching consequences.²³

3.4 Untoward consequences?

Although at face value both the argument from unnaturalness and the argument from Playing God seem to be categorical in saying that there is something wrong in genetic engineering per se, on closer look, in almost all cases they turn out to be about consequences. The only exceptions being a strict reading of the Natural Law theory that makes going against the natural order of things immoral in and by itself – whatever the consequences – and religious versions of the Playing God argument where, similarly, the consequences do not matter, it is the act of playing God that is wrong in itself. In all other cases, the real issue seems to be the feared untoward consequences.

4. Risks of harm

There are numerous schools of thought within *risk science* and varying interpretations of what a risk is, how it is assessed, and when it is seen as acceptable and when not. Very generally risk can be seen as a likelihood of something untoward happening and the severity of that untoward event further informs the evaluation of whether that risk is acceptable.^{24 25}

The main ethical issues with genetically engineered *C. elegans* lie in the risks of harm that they potentially entail, and the key is developing means to prevent those risks of ever becoming a reality. To this end, the Babots project is identifying the potential risks and finding the best counter measures available. The risk assessment needs to be proactive, so that we continually do our best to anticipate developments and events that could increase the risks or create new ones.

4.1 Accidental release

Releasing genetically altered organisms into nature is always risky as it cannot be fully predicted how they will interact with the native ecosystems. They might find their own niche and leave the systems almost unaltered, but they can also severely disturb the current balance. To prevent accidental releases, strict safety protocols need to be observed both in research and application stages.

4.2 Contained environments

In the research stages and in early applications, Babots will always be kept in contained environments (such as vertical farms or aquaponics) to minimize accidental releases.

4.3 Intentional release

If Babots live up to their promise, it could well be that sometime in the future there would be an interest to use them on a large scale, say, to clean toxic land or to optimize the quality of farmland. At that stage the behavior of genetically altered *C. elegans* will be much better known but it is reasonable to assume that risks will remain.

4.4 Safety-switches

To prepare for the future's less-contained use and, for now, to guarantee safety should the Babots start behaving in undesired ways or if the contained environment is breached, a number of safety-switches (sometimes also called "kill switches") are studied and the most appropriate ones are then chosen for use (T4.2). Especially because of their capabilities of autonomous actions, the propagation of Babots must be kept tightly controlled allowing the system operator, if and when needed, to block the propagation of the Babots in question or to terminate them permanently. At the moment, there are several candidates. We are studying a combination of temperature-sensitive mutations that result in infertility and vulval disformations upon heat exposure. Another possibility is making the Babots dependent on a lab-supplied compound to live. And there are other options. The project is also studying the possible need of using two or more safety switches simultaneously. Mutations happen in living organisms, and it is possible that mutations could overcome the applied kill-switch, but with more than one safety switch in place, the risk of this happening becomes negligible. Negligible risk is, of course, still a risk, albeit a very unlikely one. However, in terms of what is considered "safe" in biosafety, the risk doesn't have to be zero, but close enough to it. This is, arguably, within a reasonable degree of precaution.

4.5 Intentional misuse

With all new scientific developments comes a possibility of maleficent use of the technology and Babots are no exception. It is conceivable that an unscrupulous third party would wish to alter Babots to work as "biological weapons". This is something the project needs to keep in mind, but, ultimately, cannot do much about because of the requirements of open science. Mostly everything that can be used for good and can also be used for bad, say, from knives to opiates.

5. Benefits

5.1 Basic science

The most immediate benefits of the Babots project can be classified as basic science in terms of an increased understanding of *C. elegans*' behavior (swarming and individual) and, more generally, developments in gene technology, synthetic biology, synthetic neurobiology, robotics, and modelling.

5.2 Potential benefits

The main goals of the project, however, go well beyond basic science. The project will lay the foundations for groundbreaking innovations that could have a huge impact on agriculture and health care. Further, by offering an all-biological alternative to silicon or chemical based solutions, Babots contributes to the European Green Deal.

In the field of agriculture Babots could bring significant benefits to plant and yield including protecting plants from pathogens and distributing beneficial bacteria to specific targets such as the roots. Babots could also be used in cleaning polluted soil to restore healthy environment. The potential health care applications are farther in the future, but they could include Babots entering human bodies to perform specific medical procedures and leaving after the job is completed.

The genetically-based behavior guiding building blocks that the project aims to establish could, in the future, be combined in different ways and in various organisms for different applications leading to different types of Babots, such as sanitation cockroaches guided by synthetic neural connections to clean up the sewage system while staying out of the house.

Like with the potential risks, the potential benefits too need to be continually evaluated in an ongoing ethical analysis as they equally effect the harm-benefit ratio.

6. Justice considerations²⁶

Everyone agrees that justice is important, but when it comes to what people mean by the word, the interpretations vary. The figure 1 below illustrates the main ideological differences that impact our notions of justice.

When applied to matters like the Babots, the figure looks as follows.

For something to be equally just to all, it should, ideally, take into account all the different aspects of justice. Babots-project naturally fits in the top right corner of the figure, but with its sustainability goals and concern for animal welfare, it also reaches bottom-right and bottom-left corners. It is mainly the people in the top-left corner holding conservative values that are most likely to be at odds with the project and its goals. This is where we will find people concerned with unnaturalness and Playing God. These are the people most difficult to reach and almost impossible to make change their minds.²⁷ However, it is to be hoped that with the success of project like the Babots, less people will hold such strong anti-science views.

7. Public engagement

The topics covered in this framework will help us better understand the types of ethical concerns people might have with Babots. This understanding will help us in our efforts to engage with the general public and various stakeholders. The public engagement will include discussions with stakeholders, surveys, presentations and educational events. We are working with Scholz Lab's outreach personnel towards joint events and they have already created educational posters for us.

8. Future plans – towards ethics framework (Part II, D13(D4.4), M48)

The Aalto team will continue to work in close collaboration with all the other partners to remain cognizant of all the developments within the Babots project as they happen and to follow closely the ethics literature and the field of bioethics as it applies to Babots. The team will also visit Ding Laboratory and Scholz Lab to gain an increased understanding of the

science involved. The comprehensive ethics framework for Babots builds directly on top of the framework presented in this document and the framework will be continuously updated and specified.

9. An Epilogue – Future dilemmas – Animal welfare, sustainability and the green alternatives

The EU is committed to reducing *and ultimately replacing* animal use in research and testing. *C. elegans* are not currently included in the animal welfare protection, but as we learn more about the sentience of the lower animals, this could well change in the future, and as a consequence, our green alternatives could be diminishing. In the coming decades we might have to start making ethical decisions between animal welfare and the good of the environment.

¹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, *Caring for animals aiming for better science – Directive 2010/63/EU on protection of animals used for scientific purposes – Project evaluation and retrospective assessment*, Publications Office, 2018. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/59814>

² Ha et al, *Caenorhabditis elegans* as a powerful tool in natural product bioactivity research, *Applied Biological Chemistry* 65, 18(2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13765-022-00685-y>

³ Zhang et al, *Caenorhabditis elegans* as Useful Model for Studying Aging Mutations. *Front Endocrinol*, 05 Oct 2020. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2020.554994>

⁴ Crump A, Browning H, Schnell A, Burn C, Birch J. Sentience in decapod crustaceans: A general framework and review of the evidence. *Animal Sentience* 32 (2022) (1). <https://www.wellbeingintlstudiesrepository.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1691&context=animsent>

⁵ Source: Irvine E. Independence, weight and priority of evidence for sentience. *Animal Sentience* 32 (2022) (10).

<https://www.wellbeingintlstudiesrepository.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1724&context=animsent#:~:text=For%20example%2C%20the%20nematode%20C%27substantial%20evidence%20of%20sentience>

⁶ Andrews K. Does the sentience framework imply all animals are sentient? *Animal Sentience* 32 (2022) (17). DOI:10.51291/2377-7487.1737

⁷ "The likely harm to the animal should be balanced against the expected benefits of the project". Directive 2010/63/EU recital 39.

⁸ Directive 2010/63/EU (12).

⁹ Gottlieb R S (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Religion and Ecology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780195178722.001.0001>

¹⁰ <https://www.unep.org/about-un-environment-programme/faith-earth-initiative/religions-and-environmental-protection> (Last accessed on 10.09.2024)

¹¹ Camenzind S. "Kantian ethics and the animal Turn. On the contemporary defence of Kan's indirect duty view." *Animals* (Basel). 2021 Feb 16;11(2):512. Doi: 10.3390/ani11020512.

¹² Jahr, F. Bio-ethics: Reviewing the ethical relations of humans towards animals and plants [original 1927]. In Muzur, A, Sass, H-M, eds. *Fritz Jahr and the Foundations of Global Bioethics: The Future of Integrative Bioethics*. Zürich: Lit Verlag; 2011:1–4.

¹³ Jahr, F. Life sciences and the teaching of ethics: Old knowledge in new clothing [original 1926]. Miller, IM, trans. In Muzur, A, Sass, HM, eds. *1926-2016 Fritz Jahr's Bioethics: A Global Discourse*. Zürich: Lit Verlag; 2017:127–9.

¹⁴ Barsam, AP. *Reverence for Life: Albert Schweitzer's Great Contribution to Ethical Thought*. New York: Oxford University Press; 2008.

¹⁵ Häyry M. Bioethics and the value of human life. *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics* 34(2025), forthcoming.

¹⁶ Häyry M. Precaution and Solidarity. *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics* 14(2005): 199-206. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0963180105050255>

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- ¹⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, *Gaining insight into the use of animals in Science*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2023. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/836>
- ¹⁸ World Medical Association, Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects. 6th September 2022, 20.
- ¹⁹ The few benefits to animals include preservation of some endangered species, and an increased ability to eliminate parasitism, treat illnesses, and use anesthetic devices.
- ²⁰ Aristotle. *Nicomachean Ethics*.
- ²¹ For a detailed analysis of the natural law tradition, see e.g. Finnis J, *Natural Law and Natural Rights*, Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1980 & Finnis J, *Fundamentals of Ethics*, Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1984.
- ²² Takala T. The (Im)Morality of (Un)Naturalness. *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics*. 2004;13(1):15-19. doi:10.1017/S0963180104131046
- ²³ Chadwick, Ruth F. (1989). Playing God. *Cogito* 3 (3):186-193.
- ²⁴ Aven T. A risk science perspective on the discussion concerning Safety I, Safety II and Safety III. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 217 (2022), 108077
- ²⁵ Häyry M, Takala T. Genetic engineering and the risk of harm. *Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy* 1 (1998): 61-64. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1009937922873>
- ²⁶ This section is draws from our recent article on justice and sustainability (incl. the figures). Takala T, Häyry M. Justainability. *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics* 2023 (online), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0963180123000361>
- ²⁷ See e.g. Jauernig J, Uhl M, Waldhof G. Genetically engineered foods and moral absolutism: A representative study from Germany. *Science and Engineering Ethics* (2023): 29-34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-023-00454-0>